

DALIA Interchange Format (V1.4)

Short Description

Abstract

The DALIA Interchange Format (DIF) provides a framework for making the metadata and controlled vocabulary of teaching and learning materials transparent, comparable and easy to integrate into the DALIA platform. Developed by the DALIA ([Data Literacy Alliance](#)) project and in the context of the German [National Research Data Infrastructure \(NFDI\)](#), it makes the open educational resources which can be retrieved at the platform interoperable.

DIF Version 1.4 is compatible with two works of knowledge organization systems: a. [MoDALIA](#), the foundational ontology for the DALIA platform's information architecture. b. the Glossary for Open Educational Resources ([GlossOER](#)), which provides a structured vocabulary for open educational resources (OERs). GlossOER, MoDALIA, and DIF V1.4 maintain full compatibility.

Authors

Jonathan D. Geiger (<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0452-7075>, Academy of Sciences and Literature Mainz)

Petra Steiner (<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8997-2620>, Technical University of Darmstadt)

Abdelmoneim Desouki (<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2083-1277>, Technical University of Darmstadt)

Henrika M. Hüppe (<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0570-7924>, RWTH Aachen University)

Frank Lange (<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9346-6031>, RWTH Aachen)

Contributors

Susanne Arndt (<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1019-9151>, TIB - Leibniz Information Centre for Science and Technology and University):

RelatedPerson

Laura Döring (<https://orcid.org/0009-0001-7129-2018>, University of Trier): RelatedPerson

Sonja Felder (<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6969-4448>, University of Bonn): RelatedPerson

Marc Fuhrmans (<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9826-018X>, Technical University of Darmstadt): Supervisor

Jan-Michael Haugwitz (<https://orcid.org/0009-0007-3576-3947>, RWTH Aachen University) : ProjectMember

Marina Lemaire (<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4726-2481>, University of Trier): RelatedPerson

Unaiza Nadeem (Technical University of Darmstadt): ProjectMember

Juliane Röder (<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4692-2700>, Philipps University of Marburg): RelatedPerson

Jakob Voß (<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7613-4123>, Verbundzentrale des GBV (VZG): RelatedPerson

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Background

The [DALIA \(Data Literacy Alliance\) project](#) aims to develop a platform for FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable) teaching and learning materials on data literacy, data competencies, and research data management (RDM) skills within the German [National Research Data Infrastructure \(NFDI\)](#) and the RDM landscape. Such a platform thrives on the participation of users who want to search, create, manage, or use teaching and learning materials.

To achieve interoperability of teaching and learning materials, their metadata must be schematized. To this end, the DALIA Interchange Format (DIF) version 1.3 was published in 2024 (Geiger, Steiner, Desouki & Lange 2024), providing a framework for transparent, comparable, and platform-compatible metadata. The schema includes descriptions and explanations of the data fields for publishing educational resources online.

DIF V1.3 has been adopted by multiple consortia and other institutions for submitting the metadata of their open educational resources (OER). To date, 616 sets of metadata have been added to the platform using this schema. Its broad adoption establishes DIF as an important framework for community discourse. Biernacka et al. (2025) developed the latest iteration of their metadata schema for research data management educational resources, with a view to aligning it with DIF. Concurrently, the NFDI Section Metadata, Terminologies, Provenance - Working Group Cookbooks, Guidance and Best Practices, Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur and Data Literacy Alliance DALIA (2025) have published guidelines for annotating and submitting OER materials to the DALIA platform using DIF attributes. Throughout DIF's ongoing development, findings have been disseminated at various events (Geiger, Desouki et al. 2025, Geiger, Steiner et al. 2025, Steiner, Geiger et al. 2025b, Steiner, Geiger et al. 2025c, Steiner, Desouki et al. 2025) and intensively discussed within the OER research community. Key discussion forums included the OER.net working group (see Bergmann et al., 2025) and NFDI's Section Education and Training ([EduTrain](#)). As

DIF is the data model for OER metadata, and the underlying [MoDALIA](#) ontology (BMFTR DALIA project 2025) encodes it in an RDF schema, our team also engaged in intensive discussions to address requirements of compatibility.

The research community and our team identified additional requirements specifically regarding values and formats for metadata attributes. Most issues fell into these categories:

- a. Imprecise or missing intensional definitions, e.g., unclear distinctions between learning resource types like "tutorial" vs. "course".
- b. Terminology gaps, e.g., missing learning resource types such as podcasts and coding notebooks.
- c. Inconsistent domain and range specifications between metadata standards and the MoDALIA ontology. For instance, the class *supportinghost* of the Relator list by the Library of Congress (2024) was not consistent with the domain restriction of the MoDALIA ontology. This necessitated developing standardized selection lists (picklists and controlled vocabularies) with revised formal definitions. Consequently, DIF version 1.4 introduced a table dedicated for the vocabulary.

This necessitated developing standardized selection lists (picklists and controlled vocabularies). Additionally, several new attributes were introduced to enhance functionality:

- **AccessibilityFeature:** Specifies functionalities or modifications that ensure the usability of OER for all users, including those with disabilities.
- **Teaches:** Describes the competency, learning outcome, or learning objective that the target group is intended to acquire or achieve through the educational resource.
- **Contributors:** Expands the list of creators by different roles to reflect the full range of contributions to the resource.

For the picklists and vocabularies, a new description schema was developed. It consists of:

- The associated attribute
- The name of the picklist item or controlled vocabulary

- Its description
- Its IRI (Internationalized Resource Identifier)
- Specification of whether it is a picklist item or controlled vocabulary
- A comment field containing source information (when different from the IRI) and other details

This information was compiled in a concise manner and excluded most source attribution details, information on scope boundaries or schema mappings. We recognized that incorporating additional terms with precise definitions would enhance conceptual clarity. Therefore, a new **Glossary for Open Educational Resources (GlossOER)** (Steiner, Geiger et al. 2025a) was compiled for the picklist items and controlled vocabularies. This resource contains additional details, especially in the following fields:

- EntryBy: The person who added the entry.
- Definition Language: The language of the definition (e.g., en for English).
- RelationWith: Other terms that this term is related to in SKOS terminology (e.g., broadMatch, narrower, relatedMatch).
- Parent: The immediate broader term (if applicable).
- OWL Type: The OWL construct (e.g., Class, Property).
- Source of Definition: The source from which the definition is taken (if any).
- LinkOfSource/IRI of Definition: A link or IRI to the source of the definition.
- Kind of Source: How the definition was derived (Quotation, Modified quotation, See (for paraphrases), Original by DALIA team).
- Constraints/Vocabulary: The constraints on the range or the vocabulary to which the term belongs.
- Notes: Additional notes such as instructions for the selection, information on the compatibility with other standards and classifications, e.g., Zenodo, DataCite, CRediT.

Both **DIF V1.4** and **GlossOER** are compatible with the underlying [MoDALIA](#) ontology.

DIF V1.4 is **provided as a PDF document and in table form (Excel)** to convey the attributes and the picklists of the teaching and learning materials and their definitions in an easily understandable form and to facilitate communication. The picklists are provided in a separate table. For sake of conciseness, the references can be found in GlossOER that provides a complete list of references and namespaces in a separate table. DIF V1.4 also includes a legend and an example in tabular form. As a new curation form for the platform has been developed, a template for the ingestion process is no longer necessary as it was for DIF V1.3. The tables can also be transferred to technical application profiles.

We extend our sincere gratitude to the commentators of previous versions. Their valuable feedback and advice were essential for achieving DIF's present conciseness and consistency.

This project was funded by the Federal Ministry of Research, Technology, and Space (BMFTR) and the funding measure from the EU's Capacity Building and Resilience Facility with the funding code 16DWWQP07.

The authors are also looking forward to further feedback for the DALIA Interchange Format. Everyone is invited to contact petra.steiner@tu-darmstadt.de and jonathan.geiger@adwmainz.de.

DIF V1.4

attribute name	mandatory, recommended, optional	description	values (constraint type : constraint)	examples	cardinality	data type	propertyID	comment
Authors	M	The name(s) of the person(s) or organization(s) who created (wrote, made, presented ...) the resource. Can include ORCIDs or RORs.	1. for persons: surname, prename : {ORCID} (Mandatory, Recommended, Recommended) 2. for organizations: organization-name : {organization ROR > Wikidata} (Mandatory, Recommended)	(1) Mustermann, Max : { https://orcid.org/0000-0001-2345-6789 } * Musterfrau, Paula (2) Müllermeier, John * Musterkollegin, Alex * Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur : {organization https://ror.org/05qj6w324 } (3) NFDI4Chem : {organization http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q96678459 } * Example-Organization-without-identifier : {organization}	1..n	xsd:string	schema:author	Names and ORCIDs or RORs. ORCIDs are highly recommended. If there is just one name such as "chrisikraus", put the information to the surname field.
License	M	The license identifier of the resource which refers to a legal document giving official permission to do something with the resource.	non-proprietary licenses of the content of the "Identifier" column from SPDX, e.g. "CC-BY-4.0" or "CC-BY-NC-ND-3.0", other non-proprietary licenses, and "proprietary" for proprietary license	(1) CC-BY-SA-4.0 (2) proprietary	1	xsd:string	dcterms:license	"proprietary" should also be used for unclear licenses.
Link	M	The hyperlink(s) to the resource.	DOI > other URLs	(1) https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10122153 (2) https://data-affairs.affective-societies.de/lerneinheiten/forschungsethik-und-datenethik/ (3) https://doi.org/10.25656/01:29235 * https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10828758	1..n	xsd:anyURI	schema:url	
Title	M	The title (and subtitle) of the resource.	open, subtitle segmented by colon (:)	(1) cool learning resource: with a cool subtitle	1	xsd:string	dcterms:title	
AccessibilityFeature	R	Content features of the resource, such as accessible media, alternatives and supported enhancements for accessibility.	Values should be drawn from the approved vocabulary. See https://www.w3.org/community/reports/a11y-digscov-vocab/CG-FINAL-vocabulary-20241209 .		0..n	xsd:string	schema:accessibilityFeature	
Community	R	Associated community(ies) of the resource who are either the supporting organization, institution, project, body, or online group, or the recommender , or both. A community gathers users (members) and educational resources/learning paths similar to Zenodo communities. The supporting community is the organization, institution, project, body, or online group which supports the production, training, curation, dissemination, or administration of the educational resource by allocating facilities, staff, or other resources. The recommending community approves the resource.	1. picklist: consortia which are listed at https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q61658497 (NFDI) and/or at https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q61658497 and/or at https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q111582288 and/or https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q61658497 has_subidiary or is part_of and/or are https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q98270496 wd:Q105757481 or have Q61658497 (NFDI) as a parent organization > ROR name > name (string) 2. If the community is the supporting community: communityName (S), if it is recommending the OER: communityName (R), both: communityName (SR)	(1) NFDI4Culture (S) * DALIA (R) (2) fdm.nw (SR)	0..n	xsd:string	modalia:recommender and/or modalia:supportingHost	(S) defined by mrel:sht (R) defined by rec:recommender

Description	R	The description of the resource.	open	(1) This is a very cool learning resource for research data management.	0..1	xsd:string	dcterms:description	
Discipline	R	The discipline or university/college subject the learning resource belongs to.	picklist: German University Subject Classification System ("Systematik der Fächergruppen, Studienbereiche und Studienfächer") as defined by Statistisches Bundesamt https://w3id.org/kim/hochschulfaechersystematik/scheme	(1) https://w3id.org/kim/hochschulfaechersystematik/n079 (2) https://w3id.org/kim/hochschulfaechersystematik/n0 (3) https://w3id.org/kim/hochschulfaechersystematik/n42 * https://w3id.org/kim/hochschulfaechersystematik/n221	0..n	xsd:anyURI	fabio:hasDiscipline	Please choose the most specific categories (deep in the hierarchy).
FileFormat	R	The (technical) file format(s) of the resource. If the resource exists in different formats (e.g. pptx and pdf), all of them should be provided. For non-downloadable resources, e.g. streams, no format can be provided (e.g. YouTube videos).	The controlled vocabulary LoCFileFormatList which is overlapping with the MIME file types (extensions): https://mimetype.io/all-types and the fileTypes from McCallum, Patrick (2024): mimeData.json.	(1) .pptx (2) .pdf * .odt	0..n	xsd:string	dcterms:format	If a resource exists in more than one formats, it is one resource. If a resource consists of more than one parts and has different DOIs, leave the format open, and describe the file format for each of the parts (mediatype: multipart). The file format helps users to choose tools to work with the resource.
Keywords	R	Essential and characteristic topics or content of the resource.	open, but picklist recommended: https://id.loc.gov/authorities/subjects.html , https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:Main_Page , https://lobid.org/gnd	(1) data quality (2) metadata * open educational resources	0..n	xsd:string	schema:keywords	
Language	R	The language(s) of the resource, 2 char code preferred.	picklist: ISO 639-1 (two characters, e.g. en) > ISO 639-3 (three character codes) see https://id.loc.gov/vocabulary/iso639-1.html , https://www.loc.gov/standards/iso639-2/php/code_list.php , https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_ISO_639_language_codes IRIs are from the extensive lists from lexvo.org	(1) de (2) en * de	0..n	xsd:language	dcterms:language	

LearningResourceType	R	The pedagogical type of the resource: information for the educational use. This includes the most specific type: rather textbook than book.	The picklist is compiled from https://w3id.org/kim/hcrt/scheme (with exceptions), bibo, dcterms, schema, and own definitions. (Modified) definitions were also taken from other sources such as ISO standards, fabio, sio, wikidata. hcrt:application, modalia:CodeNotebook, schema:SoftwareSourceCode, bibo:Article, hcrt:assessment, modalia:BestPractices, bibo:Book, hcrt:textbook, bibo:Thesis, hcrt:case_study, modalia:Cookbook, hcrt:course, modalia:Lecture, modalia:Tutorial, bibo:Workshop, hcrt:data, hcrt:diagram, hcrt:drill_and_practice, hcrt:worksheet, hcrt:educational_game, hcrt:experiment, hcrt:index, hcrt:lesson_plan hcrt:map, modalia:Podcast, hcrt:portal, fabio:WebSite, modalia:Poster, hcrt:questionnaire, bibo:Report, hcrt:script, hcrt:sheet_music, hcrt:simulation, bibo:Webpage, hcrt:other	(1) Lecture (2) CodeNotebook * Tutorial	0..n	xsd:string	mo:hasLearningType	
MediaType	R	The general type of data content encoded in a computer file in terms of its modality (text, audio, picture etc.). The media type is to be used for user preferences for the learning style(s). If the resource consists of multiple items with different DOIs, the MediaType is "multipart" and the relations are provided in the "RelatedWork" field.	picklist: audio, video, text, presentation, code, image, multipart	(1) text * presentation (2) video	0..n	xsd:string	modalia:hasMediaType	Do not confuse this with format and learning resource type; can be "presentation" but NOT "lesson" or "experiment". If a resource consists of multiple parts and has different DOIs, describe the mediatype for each part (media type: multipart). This applies to podcasts as well.
ProficiencyLevel	R	The proposed level of proficiency in research data management and data literacy of the learners in regard to the learning content.	picklist: Novice, AdvancedBeginner, Competent, Proficient, Expert	(1) Novice * AdvancedBeginner	0..n	xsd:string	modalia:requiresProficiencyLevel	Picklist according to Dreyfus's "Novice" to "Expert". The proficiency level refers to the topic of the OER on RDM and data literacy, not to the target group. Dreyfus, Stuart E. (2004). The Five-Stage Model of Adult Skill Acquisition. In: Bulletin of Science, Technology & Society 24 (3), S. 177–181. DOI: 10.1177/0270467604264992. The labels are from Benner (1982).
PublicationDate	R	The date of first publication or broadcast.	ISO 8601 format (https://www.iso.org/iso-8601-date-and-time-format.html). If the full date is unknown, month and year (YYYY-MM) or just year (YYYY) may be used.	(1) 2024-03-31 (2) 2023-12 (3) 2022	0..1	xsd:date	schema:datePublished	

TargetGroup	R	The target group refers to the learners of the resource: A class of agents for whom the learning resource is intended or useful.	picklist: student (school), student (BA), student (MA), student (PhD), data steward, teacher (school), teacher (higher education), researcher, content provider, librarian, archivist, museum professional	(1) student (BA) * student (MA) (2) student (PhD) * data steward * researcher	0..n	xsd:string	modalia:hasTargetGroup	This does not address who is teaching. The group of (optional) teachers is not considered, only the learners are. If the learning group includes teachers, then this must be selected from the picklist.
Teaches	R	The competency, learning outcome, or learning objective the target group is intended to acquire or achieve by the educational resource.	May reference the LZM learning objectives but is not limited to them.	(1) Learners are able to name the elements and objectives of research data policies. (2) LZM v3 Lernziel 01_004_0058	0..n	xsd:string	schema:teaches	
RelatedWork	O	The relation(s) to other resources. It is required to identify the related resource by means of a URL.	DALIA: picklist based on dcterms, citedcat (adopted from DataCite), modalia (adopted from DataCite), schema. For the LINK: DOI > other URLs.	(1) isBasedOn:https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8297723 (2) isSupplementTo:https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10122153	0..n	xsd:string	dcterms:relation	
Size	O	The size of the application / package (e.g. 18 MB). In the absence of a unit (MB, KB etc.), MB will be assumed.	open	(1) 10 (2) 0.034 MB	0..1	xsd:string	schema:fileSize	Please note: MB will be assumed as the unit. This is not consistent with schema:fileSize, where KB will be assumed.
Version	O	The version of the learning resource.	open	(1) 2.3	0..1	xsd:string	schema:version	
Contributors	O	The name(s) of the person(s) or organization(s) who contributed to the resource with the roles from the picklist.	1. for persons: surname, prename : {contributor role} : {ORCID} (Mandatory, Recommended, Mandatory, Recommended) 2. for organizations: organization-name : {contributor role}: {organization ROR > Wikidata} (Mandatory, Mandatory, Recommended) picklist from https://id.loc.gov/vocabulary/relators.html . Metadata4ing, DataCite, schema. Consistent with Zenodo. Includes suggestions for CRediT categories.	(1) Lange, Frank : {ProjectMember} : {https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9346-6031} (2) Fuhrmans, Marc : {Supervisor} : {https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9826-018X} * Nadeem, Unaiza : {Other}	0..n	xsd:string	bf:contribution	

Explications

Name	Description
attribute name	metadata category; term
mandatory, recommended, optional	mandatory = required; recommended = this information is strongly recommended and should be added for interoperability; optional = not required but provides richer description
description	short definition
values (constraint type : constraint)	<p>The range of the term, often a picklist.</p> <p>* between spaces is used as separator of entries.</p> <p>> denotes the preferences.</p> <p>$A > B$ means A is preferred to B.</p> <p>Open means that the value can be chosen freely.</p> <p>Symbols such as parentheses, colon or star are used as dividers of cells with multi-entries.</p>
examples	Characteristic instances for the values of the attribute as further description. (Numbers) indicate different examples for one attribute.
cardinality	<p>The cardinality determines how many entries a value can have.</p> <p>X..Y—X is the minimum number, Y is the maximum number.</p> <p>Examples: 0..1—zero to one entry. 1..n—one to many entries.</p>
data type	xsd means XML Schema Definition, see https://www.w3.org/TR/xmlschema-2/ .
propertyID	<p>A well-established standard, e.g. <i>dcterms</i> means http://purl.org/dc/terms/ .</p> <p>Other standards can be looked up at: http://prefix.cc .</p>
comment	caveats, false friends, and other useful information

Example

Authors	Geiger, Jonathan : { https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0452-7075 } * Steiner, Petra : { https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8997-2620 } * Desouki, Abdelmoneim : { https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2083-1277 } * Hüppe, Henrika Maria : { https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0570-7924 } * Lange, Frank : { https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9346-6031 }
License	CC-BY-SA-4.0
Link	10.5281/zenodo.17871138
Title	DALIA Interchange Format
AccessibilityFeature	
Community	DALIA (SR)
Description	The DALIA Interchange Format is a metadata schema for organizing the structure of metadata of data literacy learning materials within the National Research Data Infrastructure community.
Discipline	https://w3id.org/kim/hochschulfaechersystematik/n0
FileFormat	.pdf * .xlsx
Keywords	open educational resources * metadata * schema
Language	en
LearningResourceType	Data * OtherResourceType
MediaType	text
ProficiencyLevel	AdvancedBeginner * Competent * Proficient * Expert
PublicationDate	2026-02-16
TargetGroup	DataSteward * Researcher * ContentProvider
Teaches	metadata schema

RelatedWork	isNewVersionOf: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11521029
Size	0.81 MB
Version	1.4
Contributors	Arndt, Susanne : {RelatedPerson} : {https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1019-9151} * Döring, Laura : {RelatedPerson} : {https://orcid.org/0009-0001-7129-2018} * Felder, Sonja : {RelatedPerson} : {https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6969-4448} * Fuhrmans, Marc : {Supervisor} : {https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9826-018X} * Haugwitz, Jan-Michael : {ProjectMember} : (https://orcid.org/0009-0007-3576-3947} * Lemaire, Marina : {RelatedPerson} : (https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4726-2481} * Nadeem, Unaiza : {ProjectMember} * Röder, Juliane : {RelatedPerson} : {https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4692-2700} * Voß, Jakob : {RelatedPerson} : {https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7613-4123}

Picklists and Controlled Vocabularies

attribute name	picklist Item (value) or Controlled Vocabulary	description	term IRI (or link of source)	Picklist Item (PI) Controlled Vocabulary List (CVL)	comment
License	SPDXLicenseList	The licenses included in the SPDX License List (http://spdx.org/licenses).	http://spdx.org/licenses	CVL	
License	ProprietaryLicense	A proprietary license is a type of license for a creative work in which the copyright holder retains most of the rights exclusively.	modalia:ProprietaryLicense	PI	
Community	S (supportingCommunity)	The supporting community is the organization or institution or project or body or online group which supports the production, training, curation, dissemination, or administration of the OER by allocating facilities, staff, or other resources.	modalia:supportingHost	PI	
Community	R (recommendingCommunity)	The recommending community is the organization, institution, project, body, or online group which recommends the educational resource.	modalia:recommender	PI	
Discipline	DisciplineDestatisList	The disciplines included in the German University Subject Classification System ("Systematik der Fächergruppen, Studienbereiche und Studienfächer") as defined by Statistisches Bundesamt (https://w3id.org/kim/hochschulfaechersystematik/scheme).	https://w3id.org/kim/hochschulfaechersystematik/scheme	CVL	Statistisches Bundesamt (2024). Systematik der Fächergruppen, Studienbereiche und Studienfächer. https://www.destatis.de/DE/Methoden/Klassifikationen/Bildung/studenten-pruefungstatistik.html .
FileFormat	LoCFileFormatList	The file formats included in the XML Format Description Documents of the Library of Congress, which is overlapping with the MIME file types (extensions): https://mimetype.io/all-types and the fileTypes from McCallum, Patrick (2024): mimeData.json. (https://www.loc.gov/preservation/digital/formats/fddXML/)	https://www.loc.gov/preservation/digital/formats/fddXML/	CVL	
Language	LanguageLexvoList	The languages included in the lexvo language vocabulary (http://www.lexvo.org/data/iso639-1/ and http://www.lexvo.org/data/iso639-3/).	http://www.lexvo.org/data/iso639-1/ and http://www.lexvo.org/data/iso639-3/	CVL	
LearningResourceType	Article	A written composition in prose, usually nonfiction, on a specific topic, forming an independent part of a book or other publication, as a newspaper or magazine.	bibo:Article	PI	
LearningResourceType	Assessment	The description of an activity or resource used to ensure attainment of a learning objective or learning outcome.	hcr:assessment	PI	
LearningResourceType	BestPractices	A process or method that has been shown to work well, succeeds in achieving its objective(s), is acknowledged and therefore can be recommended as an approach.	modalia:BestPractices	PI	
LearningResourceType	Book	A non-serial document that is complete in one volume or a designated finite number of volumes. A book published by a publisher is usually identified by an International Standard Book Number (ISBN), and may be manifested as a physical printed publication on paper bound in a hard or soft cover, or in electronic format.	bibo:Book	PI	
LearningResourceType	CaseStudy	A description of an actual situation, commonly involving a decision, a challenge, an opportunity, a problem or an issue.	hcr:case_study	PI	source of definition: ISO/IEC 19788-5:2014, 30, see GlossOER .

LearningResourceType	CodeNotebook	Program used to mix code, comments, and visualizations in an interactive document called notebook that can be shared, reused, and reworked in a web browser.	modalia:CodeNotebook	PI	
LearningResourceType	Cookbook	A thematic collection of useful procedures in IT.	modalia:Cookbook	PI	source of definition: https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q3689925 , see GlossOER .
LearningResourceType	Course	An educational course comprises one or more educational events and/or creative works which aims to build knowledge, competence or ability of learners.	hcr:course	PI	source of definition: https://schema.org/Course , see GlossOER .
LearningResourceType	Data	Any form of digital representation, e.g. facts, measurements, recordings, records, or observations about the world. Data may be in any format or medium taking the form of writings, notes, numbers, symbols, text, images, films, video, sound recordings, pictorial reproductions, drawings, designs or other graphical representations, procedural manuals, forms, diagrams, work flow charts, equipment descriptions, data files, data processing algorithms, or statistical records.	hcr:data	PI	source of definition: CODATA-RDM, p. 6, T4FS:0000430, see GlossOER .
LearningResourceType	Diagram	An image that illustrates the structure and/or its component substructures and/or relations with other structures by using lines, shapes, text, and other symbols.	hcr:diagram	PI	source of definition: https://schema.org/diagram , see GlossOER .
LearningResourceType	DrillAndPractice	Exercise(s) or activities for the (repetitive) training of a skill or knowledge.	hcr:drill_and_practice	PI	
LearningResourceType	Educational Game	An individual or group game intended to teach a subject, skill, or attitude.	hcr:educational_game	PI	source of definition: http://vocab.getty.edu/page/aat/300262798 , see GlossOER .
LearningResourceType	Experiment	A scientific procedure undertaken to make a discovery, test a hypothesis, or demonstrate a known fact.	hcr:experiment	PI	source of definition: ISO/IEC 19788-5:2014, 31, see GlossOER .
LearningResourceType	Lecture	An informative talk given to an audience or class and usually prepared beforehand, or the text of such a talk.	modalia:Lecture	PI	source of definition: ISO/IEC 19788-5:2014, 30, see GlossOER .
LearningResourceType	LessonPlan	Detailed descriptions or outlines for a pedagogical session. Usually includes objective(s), instructional components or methods, and assessment.	hcr:lesson_plan	PI	source of definition: http://vocab.getty.edu/page/aat/300417283 , see GlossOER .
LearningResourceType	Map	Graphic representations of a geographic area, including physical features and political boundaries, where each point corresponds to a geographical or celestial position according to a definite scale or projection. The term may also refer to similar depictions of other planets, suns, other heavenly bodies, or areas of the heavens. Maps are typically depicted on a flat medium, such as on paper, a wall, or a computer screen.	hcr:map	PI	source of definition: http://vocab.getty.edu/page/aat/300028094 , see GlossOER .
LearningResourceType	Podcast	The learning resource type podcast is an episodic series of digital audio or video files or an episode of that, which a user can download and listen to.	modalia:podcast	PI	Modified source of definition: schema:PodcastSeries, see GlossOER .
LearningResourceType	Poster	A large, usually printed placard, bill, or announcement, often illustrated, that is posted to advertise or publicize something.	modalia:Poster	PI	source of definition: schema:Poster, see GlossOER .
LearningResourceType	Questionnaire	A set of questions with a choice of answers, devised for the purposes of a survey or statistical study.	hcr:questionnaire	PI	source of definition: ISO/IEC 19788-5:2014, 32, see GlossOER .
LearningResourceType	ReferenceWork	Material to be consulted for authoritative factual information, such as a dictionary, encyclopaedia, entry, handbook, standard, or field guide, or an informative web page such as an institutional, research group or project home page.	hcr:index	PI	source of definition: fabio:ReferenceWork, see GlossOER .
LearningResourceType	Report	A document describing an account or statement describing in detail an event, situation, or the like, usually as the result of observation, inquiry, etc.	bib:Report	PI	

LearningResourceType	Script	A script or scriptum is a textbook or study materials that include the content of a lecture series or course.	hcr:script	PI	
LearningResourceType	SheetMusic	A piece of musical notation.	hcr:sheet_music	PI	
LearningResourceType	Simulation	The reproducing of characteristics, conditions, and/or systems, often by the use of a model or a representation.	hcr:simulation	PI	source of definition: ISO/IEC 19788-5:2014, 32, see GlossOER .
LearningResourceType	SoftwareApplication	A software application is software that can be directly executed by some processing unit.	hcr:application	PI	
LearningResourceType	SoftwareSourceCode	Source code (also referred to as source or code) is the version of software as it is originally written in plain text (i.e., human readable alphanumeric characters).	schema:SoftwareSourceCode	PI	
LearningResourceType	Textbook	Book used as standard work for the formal study of a particular subject.	hcr:textbook	PI	
LearningResourceType	Thesis	A document created to summarize research findings associated with the completion of an academic degree.	bibo:Thesis	PI	
LearningResourceType	Tutorial	A course with strong instructional components containing exercises, information, etc.	modalia:Tutorial	PI	source of definition: ISO/IEC 19788-5:2014, 32, see GlossOER .
LearningResourceType	Webpage	A web page is an online document available (at least initially) on the world wide web.	bibo:Webpage	PI	
LearningResourceType	WebPortal	A website that integrates applications, processes and services.	hcr:portal	PI	source of definition: https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q186165 , see GlossOER .
LearningResourceType	Worksheet	A sheet containing exercises or tasks to be completed for the purpose of imparting knowledge, attitudes, or skills.	hcr:worksheet	PI	
LearningResourceType	Workshop	A seminar, discussion group, or the like, that emphasizes the exchange of ideas and the demonstration and application of techniques, skills, etc. in a specialized field or occupation.	bibo:Workshop	PI	
LearningResourceType	WebSite	A collection of related web pages containing text, images, videos and/or other digital assets that are addressed relative to a common Uniform Resource Locator (URL). A web site is hosted on at least one web server, accessible via a network such as the Internet or a private local area network.	fabio:WebSite	PI	
LearningResourceType	OtherResourceType	A learning resource type that is not covered by the other listed categories.	hcr:other	PI	
MediaType	Audio	A resource has the media type audio if it mainly consists of aural material.	schema:AudioObject	PI	
MediaType	Video	A resource has the media type video if it mainly consists of moving images.	schema:VideoObject	PI	
MediaType	Text	A resource has the media type text if it mainly consists of written or writing materials.	schema:Text	PI	
MediaType	Presentation	A resource has the media type presentation if it mainly consists of slides.	schema:PresentationDigitalDocument	PI	
MediaType	Code	A resource has the media type code if it mainly consists of programming code.	modalia:Code	PI	
MediaType	Image	A resource has the media type image if it mainly consists of (a) still image(s).	schema:ImageObject	PI	
MediaType	Multipart	A resource has the media type 'multipart' if it consists of more than one part, each of a different media type.	modalia:Multipart	PI	

ProficiencyLevel	Novice	Novice learners are individuals who are unpracticed and have little to no knowledge in the field of learning. They lack a fundamental understanding of basic concepts and are not yet able to assess situations and tasks effectively. They require introductions, descriptions, and guidelines.	modalia:Novice	PI	picklist item according to Dreyfus (2004) "The Five-Stage Model of Adult Skill Acquisition" and Benner (1982): novice, advanced beginner, competent, proficient, and expert, see GlossOER .
ProficiencyLevel	AdvancedBeginner	Advanced beginner learners are individuals who possess some basic knowledge of the field of learning and are able to recognize patterns. They require instructions and need to follow examples.	modalia:Beginner	PI	picklist item according to Dreyfus (2004) "The Five-Stage Model of Adult Skill Acquisition" and Benner (1982): novice, advanced beginner, competent, proficient, and expert, see GlossOER .
ProficiencyLevel	Competent	Competent learners have gained moderate experience in the field of learning through consistent application of skills. They possess significant knowledge of the field, are able to evaluate features, and can efficiently and accurately apply various plans and rules according to situations and tasks. At this stage, problem-solving and decision-making are accompanied by emotional involvement.	modalia:Competent	PI	picklist item according to Dreyfus (2004) "The Five-Stage Model of Adult Skill Acquisition" and Benner (1982): novice, advanced beginner, competent, proficient, and expert, see GlossOER .
ProficiencyLevel	Proficient	Proficient learners possess a strong foundation of knowledge and skills, enabling them to perform tasks with a high degree of accuracy and efficiency. They are able to recognize patterns in situations and tasks, and can develop complex solutions through conscious deliberation.	modalia:Proficient	PI	picklist item according to Dreyfus (2004) "The Five-Stage Model of Adult Skill Acquisition" and Benner (1982): novice, advanced beginner, competent, proficient, and expert, see GlossOER .
ProficiencyLevel	Expert	Expert learners are individuals knowledgeable in a specialized field, particularly people with the special skill or knowledge representing mastery of a particular subject. They possess a deep and comprehensive understanding of the subject matter, enabling them to quickly and intuitively analyze new situations and tasks, and develop complex solutions without conscious deliberation.	modalia:Expert	PI	picklist item according to Dreyfus (2004) "The Five-Stage Model of Adult Skill Acquisition" and Benner (1982): novice, advanced beginner, competent, proficient, and expert, see GlossOER .
TargetGroup	StudentSchool	A student who is attending a school for achieving levels 1, 2, or 3 of the 2011 version of the International Standard Classification of Education structure.	modalia:StudentSchool	PI	source from: Unesco2012:32-42 - UNESCO Institute for Statistics (2012). International Standard Classification of Education (ISCED) 2011. Paris: UNESCO. https://uis.unesco.org/sites/default/files/documents/international-standard-classification-of-education-isced-2011-en.pdf , see GlossOER .
TargetGroup	BachelorStudent	A student of higher education who is attending a university or college (e.g. in USA, GB) for achieving level 6 of the 2011 version of the International Standard Classification of Education structure.	modalia:BachelorStudent	PI	Programmes at ISCED level 6, or Bachelor's or equivalent level, are often designed to provide participants with intermediate academic and/or professional knowledge, skills and competencies, leading to a first degree or equivalent qualification. Programmes at this level are typically theoretically-based but may include practical components and are informed by state of the art research and/or best professional practice. They are traditionally offered by universities and equivalent tertiary educational institutions. (Unesco2012, 51), see GlossOER .
TargetGroup	Master'sStudent	A student of higher education who is attending a university or college (e.g. in USA, GB) for achieving level 7 of the 2011 version of the International Standard Classification of Education structure.	modalia:MastersStudent	PI	Programmes at ISCED level 7, or Master's or equivalent level, are often designed to provide participants with advanced academic and/or professional knowledge, skills and competencies, leading to a second degree or equivalent qualification. Programmes at this level may have a substantial research component but do not yet lead to the award of a doctoral qualification. Typically, programmes at this level are theoretically-based but may include practical components and are informed by state of the art research and/or best professional practice. They are traditionally offered by universities and other tertiary educational institutions. (Unesco 2012, 55), see GlossOER .

TargetGroup	PhDStudent	A student of higher education who is attending a university or college (e.g. in USA, GB) for achieving level 8 of the 2011 version of the International Standard Classification of Education structure.	modalia:PhDStudent	PI	Programmes at ISCED level 8, or doctoral or equivalent level, are designed primarily to lead to an advanced research qualification. Programmes at this ISCED level are devoted to advanced study and original research and are typically offered only by research-oriented tertiary educational institutions such as universities. Doctoral programmes exist in both academic and professional fields. (Unesco2012, 59), see GlossOER .
TargetGroup	DataSteward	Data Steward is an umbrella term for numerous support roles that involve the creation, management and usage of research data. These can be very hands-on roles involving daily data analysis or roles that are more policy and advising-focused. A data steward facilitates the quality, integrity and access to (meta)data in a manner that is consistent with the appropriate laws and institutional policies, ensuring professional treatment of data throughout all stages of the research project. Data Stewards are an important part of scientific communities, supporting recommended data management practices and supporting researchers in these efforts. Often their roles overlap with those of data managers and other professionals who curate data. Data Stewards tend to have scientific backgrounds and can have the technical skills needed to analyse and manage both data and software.	obo:T4FS_0000178	PI	ScopeNote: This term primarily refers to scientific communities, with less relevance to industry. Note that the meaning of this term may differ in industrial contexts. For more information, see GlossOER .
TargetGroup	TeacherSchool	A teacher who is working at a school for levels 1, 2, or 3 of the 2011 version of the International Standard Classification of Education structure.	modalia:TeacherSchool	PI	see Unesco2012:32-42 - UNESCO Institute for Statistics (2012). International Standard Classification of Education (ISCED) 2011. Paris: UNESCO. https://uis.unesco.org/sites/default/files/documents/international-standard-classification-of-education-isced-2011-en.pdf .
TargetGroup	TeacherHigherEducation	A teacher who is working at a university or college (e.g. USA, GB) for levels 6, 7, or 8 of the 2011 version of the International Standard Classification of Education structure.	modalia:TeacherHigherEducation	PI	
TargetGroup	Researcher	A person or a group who attempts to answer research questions, establish facts, and reach new conclusions by systematically investigating and studying materials and sources, observing, or conducting experiments in a particular field relevant to the questions.	modalia:Researcher		source of definition: FrameNetProject2020, frame:Research, lexical unit: researcher, see GlossOER .
TargetGroup	ContentProvider	Person or group who is providing (an) OER.	modalia:ContentProvider	PI	
TargetGroup	Librarian	A person who administers and maintains libraries or collections of information, for public or private access through reference or borrowing. Librarians work in a variety of settings, such as educational institutions, museums, and corporations, and with various types of informational materials, such as books, periodicals, recordings, films, and databases. Tasks may include acquiring, cataloging, and circulating library materials, and user services such as locating and organizing information, providing instruction on how to access information, and setting up and operating a library's media equipment.	obo:OCCO_25402200	PI	source of definition: OccO: Occupation Ontology, see GlossOER .
TargetGroup	Archivist	A person who appraises, edits, and directs safekeeping of permanent records and historically valuable documents. Participates in research activities based on archival materials.	obo:OCCO_25401100	PI	source of definition: OccO: Occupation Ontology, see GlossOER .
TargetGroup	MuseumProfessional	A person who works in a museum and has specialized knowledge, training, or expertise related to museums and their functions.	modalia:MuseumProfessional	PI	
RelatedWork	isPartOf	A related resource in which the described resource is physically or logically included.	dcterms:isPartOf	PI	
RelatedWork	hasPart	A related resource that is included either physically or logically in the described resource.	dcterms:hasPart	PI	

RelatedWork	isContinuedBy	A related resource which is the direct continuation of the described resource. This applies to a story, a series of lessons, a serial, a journal etc. Successors typically form part of a common whole—such as a series of lectures.	citedcat:isContinuedBy	PI	source of definition: https://github.com/europeana/metis-schema/blob/master/src/main/resources/schema_xsd/EDM-COMMON-MAIN.xsd , see GlossOER .
RelatedWork	continues	A related resource which is the direct predecessor of the described resource. This applies to a story, a series of lessons, a serial, a journal etc. Predecessors typically form part of a common whole—such as a series of lectures.	citedcat:continues	PI	source of definition: https://github.com/europeana/metis-schema/blob/master/src/main/resources/schema_xsd/EDM-COMMON-MAIN.xsd , see GlossOER .
RelatedWork	isSupplementTo	Resource that is complemented by the described augmenting resource.	citedcat:isSupplementTo	PI	
RelatedWork	isSupplementedBy	Resource that complements the predominant described resource.	citedcat:isSupplementedBy	PI	
RelatedWork	references	A related resource that is referenced, cited, or otherwise pointed to by the described resource.	dcterms:references	PI	
RelatedWork	isReferencedBy	A related resource that references, cites, or otherwise points to the described resource.	dcterms:isReferencedBy	PI	
RelatedWork	describes	A related resource that is described by the resource.	modalia:describes	PI	
RelatedWork	isDescribedBy	A related resource that provides a description (detailed account) of the described resource. This can be a manual, instructions, a documentation, a cookbook, a README file, or something similar.	modalia:isDescribedBy	PI	
RelatedWork	isTranslationOf	The related resource that this OER has been translated from. When a resource is shared in one language, then later translated to another language, use "isTranslationOf" to link the translation to the original.	modalia:isTranslationOf	PI	If the direction of the translation is intransparent or the relatedWork was created in parallel to the resource, hasTranslation is suitable. The label is taken from DataCite, also the modified definition.
RelatedWork	hasTranslation	A related resource that is a translation of the content of the described resource. When a resource is shared in one language, then later translated to another language, use "hasTranslation" to link the original resource to its translation. When a resource is released at the same time in multiple languages, use "hasTranslation" to connect the works to each other in both directions.	modalia:hasTranslation	PI	In contrast to schema: workTranslation, this can be used as symmetric relation. The label is taken from DataCite.
RelatedWork	isPreviousVersionOf	The related work is a new version or edition of the described resource, where the new version has been modified or updated.	modalia:isPreviousVersionOf	PI	For the sources, see GlossOER .
RelatedWork	isNewVersionOf	The related work is a previous version or edition of the described resource, of which the described resource has been modified or updated.	modalia:isNewVersionOf	PI	For the sources, see GlossOER .
RelatedWork	isVersionOf	A related resource of which the described resource is a version or edition. Can be used instead of isPreviousVersionOf and isNewVersionOf, if the sequence of versioning is unclear.	modalia:isVersionOf	PI	Adaptations should be covered by isBasedOn.
RelatedWork	isIdenticalTo	The related work is the same as the described resource but is saved on another location, maybe another institution.	modalia:isIdenticalTo	PI	
RelatedWork	isBasedOn	A resource from which this work is derived or from which it is a modification or adaptation.	schema:isBasedOn	PI	
RelatedWork	replaces	A related resource that is supplanted, displaced, or superseded by the described resource.	dcterms:replaces	PI	
RelatedWork	isReplacedBy	A related resource that supplants, displaces, or supersedes the described resource.	dcterms:isReplacedBy	PI	
Contributors	Annotator	A person who makes manuscript annotations on an item.	modalia:Annotator	PI	source of definition: https://id.loc.gov/vocabulary/relators/ann.html , see GlossOER .

Contributors	ContactPerson	Person with knowledge of how to access, troubleshoot, or otherwise field issues related to the resource.	modalia:ContactPerson	PI	source of definition DataCite, m4i, see GlossOER . scopeNote from the source: May also be the "Point of Contact" in an organisation that controls access to the resource, if that organisation is different from the Publisher, Distributor, and Data Manager.
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Contributors	DataCurator	A data curator is a person tasked with reviewing, enhancing, cleaning, or standardizing metadata and the associated data submitted for storage, use, and maintenance within a data centre or repository.	modalia:DataCurator	PI	source of definition DataCite, m4i, see GlossOER . More scope information in the GlossOER.
Contributors	DataManager	Person (or organisation with a staff of data managers, such as a data centre) responsible for maintaining the finished resource.	modalia:DataManager	PI	source of definition DataCite, m4i, see GlossOER . scopeNote from the source: The work done by this person or organisation ensures that the resource is periodically 'refreshed' in terms of software/hardware support, is kept available or is protected from unauthorized access, is stored in accordance with industry standards, and is handled in accordance with the records management requirements applicable to it.
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Contributors	Interviewee	A person, family, or organization responsible for creating or contributing to a resource by responding to an interviewer, usually a reporter, pollster, or some other information gathering agent.	modalia:Interviewee	PI	source of definition: https://id.loc.gov/vocabulary/relators/ive.html , see GlossOER .
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Contributors	SoftwareDeveloper	A person primarily responsible for programming, software development, designing computer programs, implementation of the computer code and supporting algorithms, and testing of existing code components.	modalia:SoftwareDeveloper	PI	source of definition: CRedIt, p. 8, see GlossOER .
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Contributors	Speaker	A performer contributing to a resource by speaking words, such as a lecture, speech, etc.	modalia:Speaker	PI	source of definition http://id.loc.gov/vocabulary/relators/spk , see GlossOER .
Contributors	Sponsor	Person or organisation that issued a contract or under the auspices of which a work has been written, printed, published, developed, etc.	modalia:Sponsor	PI	source of definition DataCite, m4i, see GlossOER . scopeNote from the source: Includes organisations that provide in-kind support, through donation, provision of people or a facility or instrumentation necessary for the development of the resource, etc.
Contributors	Supervisor	Designated administrator over one or more groups/teams working to produce a resource, or over one or more steps of a development process.	modalia:Supervisor	PI	source of definition DataCite, m4i, see GlossOER .
Contributors	Teacher (contributor)	A performer contributing to a resource by giving instruction or providing a demonstration.	modalia:TeacherContributorRole	PI	source of definition http://id.loc.gov/vocabulary/relators/tch , see GlossOER . Not identical with modalia:TeacherRole.
Contributors	Translator	A person, organization, or automated system responsible for converting the content of a resource from one language into another, preserving its meaning and intended message.	modalia:Translator	PI	source of definition DataCite, see GlossOER .
Contributors	WorkPackageLeader	A Work Package is a recognized data product, not all of which is included in publication. The package, instead, may include notes, discarded documents, etc. The Work Package Leader is responsible for ensuring the comprehensive contents, versioning, and availability of the Work Package during the development of the resource.	modalia:WorkPackageLeader	PI	source of definition DataCite, m4i, see GlossOER .
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